

INFLUENCE OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION MANAGEMENT ON THE QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: In this article, opinions are expressed about management, the culture of management of an educational institution and its impact on the quality and effectiveness of education.

Key words: management, management culture, educational quality, educational effectiveness.

The quality of education is the actuality of acquired knowledge and concrete conditions and applications for the achievement of concrete goals and the improvement of quality. The quality of knowledge is determined by the fundamental nature, depth and relevance of work after graduation.

The question of how to improve the quality of education in a higher education institution or how to turn it into a successful educational institution is considered one of the problems today. Until now, there has been no universal tool for measuring the quality of education. However, a number of indicators such as successful universities cannot be ignored.

Firstly, it is the presence of clear goals and development plans that are open and understandable to every university employee. Secondly, this is the integrity of the educational task, which means effective cooperation between all departments of the university, as well as mutual cooperation between teachers and students.

V-tertiaks are qualified teaching staff who regularly improve their qualifications. Also, the effectiveness of higher education can be measured by the availability of educational programs, large libraries, computers and other sources

of information that students need. Recently, due to the increased attention of the state to improving the quality of education, more and more attention is paid to modern technologies that are used at the university and help to achieve the maximum positive synergistic effect.

To improve the quality of education, higher education assignments must have clear goals and ways of achieving them. In fact, the main goal of all training sessions is the same - to provide the country with qualified specialists. But achieving these goals may be entirely possible only by overcoming a number of problems, for example: regular growth and constant updating of information for teaching students, reducing classroom time for the educational process, and uniform standards for student training. It is necessary to comply, to work taking into account one's own interests, capabilities and personal interests, that is, the teacher must structure the educational process in such a way as to take into account all these features. This can only be achieved through the introduction of automated higher education management systems in the organization of the educational process. This helps each student find an individual approach, track it and regulate the time for elimination. Most higher education institutions offer three forms of study: full-time, part-time and distance learning. And if during full-time study the student is in constant direct communication with the applicant, receives questions and advice, then with full-time and distance learning there are no such opportunities. Such students study subjects on their own, find answers and must engage in learning. material. However, questions often remain, and the teacher's advice becomes necessary. For such students, it is important to get advice from a teacher and receive assignments to complete independently via information technology, the Internet, without personal meetings. In addition, constant contact with higher education is necessary to increase motivation for learning, control the student's feelings in front of the teacher, and create a systematic approach to the entire educational

process. The process is organized in such a way that it can be easily constructed and provides access to educational information and activities. It is necessary to gradually create an information space in the field of higher education. This helps to respond in a timely manner and correct inconsistencies with the set automation goals. According to various existing models, quality systems and higher education institutions depend on various factors. As a result of the quality of specialist training, the quality of higher education graduates and the educational process, this has led to a decline in the reputation of the higher education system at the national and international levels. Izvestny ob'ektivnye and sub'ektivnye prichiny slojivsheysya situatsii:

- this is a significant decrease in real wages
- salaries of higher education teachers - which led to the departure of qualified, highly qualified employees

teaching staff - natural old age, lack of motivation to work, enough time to ensure the quality of new work, youth of staff, declining level of training.

- in connection with unnecessary compensation of financial resources by drivers “on the other side”; The collapse of the economy associated with the economic crisis, rising unemployment and, as a result, lack of motivation for education.

Theoretical and practical approaches to the formation of systemic quality of education.

Training in the higher education system was basically aimed at obtaining relevant knowledge. The state educational standard and training programs were aimed at mastering special organizational didactic units of Zaedets, general directions, and the international educational community. Thus, the current situation in higher education institutions cannot be called positive. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the activities of universities based on the main list of approved accreditation indicators for state regulation of education and

comprehensive control of educational institutions.

Increasing the knowledge and competence of managers in managing an educational institution, management culture and its democratization is one of the pressing issues of a modern market economy. Before we talk about managing an institution, what is management itself? We need to answer such questions.

Management is recognized as a factor in the management of educational participants in the educational process and educational system; it is an activity inherent in any society and arising from the need for life and livelihood. Management culture means that the exercise leader controls himself in any situation, is calm and courteous, makes decisions and manages, having a deep understanding of pedagogical and psychological knowledge. The management of an educational institution, as well as the manager's attitude towards his subordinate employees, and the participation of employees in decision making have a significant impact on the quality and effectiveness of education in this institution. After all, one of the main rules of management is to put quality at the forefront. In fact, quality is an important aspect of the work process, it affects the well-being of stakeholders, in short, it serves to satisfy their needs. Quality ensures the mobilization of all resources for the efforts of participants in the labor process.

The attitude of the head of the institution towards employees, that is, encouraging them in the right place, correct assessment of their achievements, serves to increase the employee's energy for work and professional activities. This, in turn, ensures that the lesson taught by the teacher is comprehensively consistent and rich. The quality and innovation of the lessons taught by the teacher are of great importance in increasing the speed of student learning and the rating of the educational institution. Quality in management undoubtedly means efficiency. Because these two concepts - quality and efficiency - are relevant concepts that complement each other in education management. In

particular, efficiency means the ability to achieve the desired result in educational management.

The teaching profession has been formed, and management, that is, pedagogical management, is being formed along with it. The consistent implementation of management in each educational institution testifies to the managerial ethics of the leader, administrative and economic activities, as well as theoretical and practical knowledge of ethics and practical recommendations aimed at the quality implementation of the educational process.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the use of foreign experience in improving the quality of higher education, the use of foreign experience in the system for assessing the quality of education is a system of educational activities. The use of foreign experience in assessing the quality of education is the construction of an “Education System” that has high strategic potential, is able to quickly adapt to changes in the external environment, is competitive in the long term, and consistently achieves high results. . . In modern market conditions, education quality management is becoming increasingly important. To achieve success in education, it is necessary to have certain competitive advantages, work in an attractive system and, of course, apply the foreign experience of Uzbekistan and regularly improve it in order to improve the quality of education. Educational management studies the management of an educational institution and, without a doubt, covers educational processes. If an educational institution is fairly managed by the leader and decisions are made taking into account the views of the staff, this will certainly have a significant impact on the quality and effectiveness of education. This is reflected in student performance and staff performance.

References.

1. 1. Xamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "EVACUATION OF THE LEVEL OF CONFLICTS IN CONFLICT SITUATIONS BETWEEN ADOLESCENTS." *Confrencea* 1.1 (2023): 23-27.
<https://confrencea.org/index.php/confrenceas/article/view/372/375>
2. Khamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "MASTERY OF MANAGING PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION STUDY, GENERALIZATION AND DISSEMINATION OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCE." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 1217-1222.
<https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/4627/4322>
3. Khamidovna M. I. CAUSES OF FAMILY CONFLICTS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 12. – C. 870-872.
<https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3156/2907>
4. PF – 5847 – net. Concept of systemic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. 08.10.2019
5. Deyatlov V. A. Current issues in personnel management. -Moscow, 2001.-69.
6. Garayeva A.K. The ever-increasing role of information technologies and the higher education system // *Distance and virtual learning* -2011 No. 6 p.45-50.
7. Plaksiy S.I. Quality indicators of higher education // *Knowledge. Understanding. Qualification. Information and humanitarian portal*. 2004.
8. Nurmurodov T.I. Experience of N.D.K.I in the integration of science, education and production. Prospects for the development of higher education:

Collection-T.: E-LINE PRESS LLC, 2013.

9. Vahabov A. and the second. Foreign investment. -T., publishing house "Finance". 2010.-324 st.

10. Israilov B.I. increasing the role of economic intermediaries in the development of innovative corporate cooperation in the education system

11. Shoyusupova N., Ataniyazova M.B. Personnel management. Tashkent-2016. Page 22

12. Educational management. Qdpi Educational and methodological complex. Page 69

13. Khodzhiakhmedov G` and others. Quality control. Tashkent-2012. Page 5

14. Shoyusupova N., Ataniyazova M.B. Personnel management. Tashkent-2016. Page 26

15. Akhliddinov R., Saidov Kh and others. Independence and education. - Tashkent: "Shark", 2001.

16. Yuldosheva D. Didactic foundations for setting educational goals based on the national personnel training program. - T.: Science, 2006.

17. <https://gejournal.net/index.php/IJSSIR/article/view/1456/1358>

18. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3004>

19. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3262>

20. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3263>